

BUYUK IPAK YO'LI

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Osiyo xalqaro unversteti tarix yo'nalishi talabasi.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola qadimgi Buyuk Ipak yo'li xaqida. Buyuk Ipak yo'li XVI asrgacha ya'ni buyuk geografik kashfiyotlar davriga qadar sharq va g'arb mamlakatlari orasida katta ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan. Tarixchilar dastlab bu yo'lni buyuk meridanal yo'l deb ham nomlashgan.

Kalit So'zlar: Xitoy, Xan, Qang', Parfiya, Rim, Ferdinand Paul Vilgilim Rixitgofen, U-di, Chjan Siyan, Xun, Xotan, Davan, Baqtrya, Zariasp, Fu Xao, In, Xenan, A'non, Ishtaxry, Nautak.

THE GREAT SILK ROAD

Abstract. Three articles about the Great Silk Road. The Great Silk Road was of great importance between Eastern and Western countries until the 16th century, that is, until the era of great geographical discoveries. Historians called this road the Great Meridian Road.

Key Words: China, Han, Kang', Parthia, Rome, Ferdinand Paul Wilhelm Richithofen, U-di, Zhang Siyan, Hun, Khotan, Davan, Bactria, Zariasp, Fu Hao, In, Henan, A'non, Ishtakry, Nautak.

ВЕЛИКИЙ ШЕЛКОВЫЙ ПУТЬ

Аннотация. Три статьи о великом Великом Шелковом пути. Великий шелковый путь имел большое значение между странами Востока и Запада вплоть до XVI века, то есть до эпохи великих географических открытий. Историки называли эту дорогу Великой меридиональной дорогой.

Ключевое Слова: Китай, Хань, Канг, Парфия, Рим, Фердинанд Пауль Вильгельм Рихитхофен, У-ди, Чжан Сян, Хун, Хотан, Давань, Бактрия, Зариасп, Фу Хао, Инь, Хэнань, Анон, Иштакри, Наутак.

KIRISH

Milodan avvalgi I ming yillikning oxiri milodiy I ming yillikning boshlariga kelib Tinch okeanidan Atlantika okeanigacha cho'zilgan ulkan geografik hudud madaniyati yuksak rivojlangan sivilizatsiyalarning yagona tizimiga birlashadi. Bu hududda joylashgan davlatlar Xitoydagi Xan saltanati, kushon podsholigi, Qang' davlati, Parfiya davlati, Rim saltanatining chegaralari bir-biriga tutash edi. Ushbu zabardast saltanatlar va sivilizatsiyalar markazlari insoniyat tarixida birinchi bo'lib "Buyuk Ipak yo'li" deb nomlanuvchi bir yo'l bilan bog'landilar.

Umumiy uzunligi 12 ming km bo'lib Xitoydan O'rta Yer dengizining shimoliy qirg'oqlariga qadar cho'zilgan bu yo'l orqali ko'pgina xalqlar va elatlar turli tamonlana munosabatlar o'rnatadilar. Podsholarning o'zaro elchilar yuborishlari, bir-biriga turli xil sovg'alar in'om etishlari an'anaga aylandi. Sharq bilan g'arb madaniyatining bir-biriga ta'siri kuchaydi. Bu yo'lga XIX asrning ikkinchi yarmida ya'ni 1877-yilda nemis olimi Ferdinand Paul Vilgilim Rixitgofen tamonidan ilk marta "Ipak Yo'li" degan nom tilga olinadi va keyinchalik butun dunyo tadqiqotchilari tamonidan e'tirof etiladi.

Asosiy qisim

Bu Ipak yo'ling qisqacha tarixiga nazar tashalaydigan bo'sak, Xan imperiyasining U-di hukmronligi davrida (mil. avv.140.86) mamlakatning g'arbiy hududlariga bo'lgan qiziqish kuchaydi. Xitoyliklar bu hududlarga bo'lgan qiziqish kuchaydi. Xitoyliklar bu hududlarda o'sha davrda ancha xavfli bo'lgan harbiy kuchlar Xunlar bilan to'qnashadilar. Xunlarga qarshi ittifoqchilar topish uchun imperator U-di mil.avv.138- yilda diplomat, sayohatchi va savdogar Chjan Syanni O'rta Osiyoga jo'natadi. Chjan Syan bir necha yil xunlar qo'lida asirlikda bo'ladi va mil.avv.128-126-yillarda Farg'ona (Davanga) keladi. Davan hokim dorlari bilan harbiy ittifoq tuzishda muvoffaqiyatsizlikka uchragan Chjan Syan ko'p qiyinchiliklardan so'ng yurtiga qaytib keladi. Chjan Syan missiyasi Xitoy uchun g'arbiy o'lkalarga chiqishda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'ldi. Miloddan avvalgi 111-115-yillarda imperator U-di Parfiya podsholariga, Qang' davlatlariga keyinroq esa Baqtirya yerlariga o'z elchilarini yuborib ular bilan diplomatik va savdo aloqalarini o'rnatadi. Shu tariqa miloddan avvalgi II-I asrlarda sharq bilan g'arbni bog'lovchi Buyuk Ipak yo'liga asos solinadi. Ammo bugungi kunda olib borilayotgan ko'plab tadqiqotlar va izlanishlar natijasida bu faktni to'ri deb ham atay olmaymiz. Chunki elchi bu yo'lning qadimiy Xitoy bilan Turkiston shaharlarigacha bo'lgan qismini ochib bergan.

Elchigacha bo'lgan ming yildan ortiq davr davomida Yevropa va Yaqin Sharq davlatlaridan O'zbekiston orqali Xitoyga boradigan savdo yo'li mavjud bo'lgan. Unda asosan turkistonliklar faoliyat ko'rsatgan. Xitoy manbalariga chuqurroq yondashilsa "Buyuk Ipak yo'li" kamida 3-4 ming yillik tarixga ega ekanligi ma'lum bo'ladi. Buni arxeologik manbalar ham tasdiqlaydi. Masalan so'ngi 30 yil davomida Xitoy arxeologlari tamonidan qadimiy Xitoy viloyatlaridan topilgan ashyoviy dalillar ushbu fikrni tasdiqlaydi. Chunonchi 1976- yili Xenan o'lkasi A'non viloyatida joylashgan In xonligi hukmdori Udinning (mil.av. 1365-1324) kanizagi Fu Xao qabri Xitoy arxeologlari tamonidan ochilganda uning ichidan ko'p miqdorda qosh toshidan yasalgan buyumlar topilgan. Maxsus tekshirish va tadqiqotlar natijasida qabr ichidan olingan 1928 ta buyumdan 756 tasi oq, qora, yashil, novot va sariq rangli qosh toshlaridan nihoyatda ustalik bilan bundan 3,5 ming yil muqaddam Xitoy bilan Xo'tan orasida savdo yo'li mavjud bo'lganliging isbotidir.

Hozirgi Shinjong Uyg'ur Muxtor o'lkasida ham miloddan avvalgi IV-III asrlarga oid qabrlar ichida Xitoyda lakdan yasalgan likopcha, bronza va boshqa metaldan yasalgan oynaklar topilgan. Ushbu ashyoviy dalillar Chjan Syangacha ham qadimiy Xitoydan g'arb tamonga qarab yuriladigan yo'llar mavjud ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

Miloddan avvalgi IV-III asrlarda qadimiy Xitoyda ishlab chiqilgan ipak matolarning Hindiston va Yevropa mamlakatlarida keng tarqalishi ham Chjan Syanning Farg'onaga borishidan avval Xitoyda Janubiy Osiyo va Yevropa mamlakatlariga O'zbekiston orqali o'tadigan qadimiy savdo yo'li borligini ko'rsatadi.

O'z davrida nihoyatda katta ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan bu yo'lning dastlabki tarmog'I Xitoydagi Sian shahridan boshlanib, Sharqiy Turkiston O'rta Osiyo Eron Mesapatamiya orqali O'rta Yer deneziga qadar cho'zilgan. Akademik Ahmadali Asqarov ma'lumotlariga qaraganda "Buyuk Ipak yo'li" yuqorida ta'kidlanganidek Xitoyning qadimiy markazi Siandan boshlanib Lanchjau orqali Duxungach boradi. U yerda u ikki tarmoqqa bo'linadi.

- 1.Janubi-g'arbiy tarmoq
- 2.SHimoli g'arbiy tarmoq

Ipak yo'lining janubi-g'arbiy tarmog'I Taklamokon sahrosi orqali Xotan (Xo'tan) undan Yorkentga kelib Pomir tog'ining daralari orqali Voxanga, undan Baqtiryanning bosh shahri Zariaspga (Balx) kelgan. Balxda yo'l yana uch tarmoqqa ajraladi. G'arbiy tarmog'I Mavrga, Janubiy tarmog'i Hindistonga, shimoliy tarmog'i Darband, Nautak, Samarqandga qarab keladi.

Ipak yo'lining shimoli-g'arbiy tarmog'I esa Dunxundan Bami, Kuchi, Turfon orqali Tarim vohasiga ya'ni Qashqarga boradi. Bu yerda Toshqo'rgo'n orqali O'zgan, O'sh, Quva, Axsikent, Popga undan keyin Asht orqali Xo'jand, Zomin, Jizzax, so'ngra Samarqandda Nautak yo'li bilan birlashadi. Yo'l Samarqanddan g'arbga Dobusiya, Malik cho'li orqali Buxoro va Romitanga Undan Varaxsha orqali Boykent va Farobga borib Amul shahriga o'tadi. Amulda Marvdan Urganch tamon Amu bo'ylab kelayotgan yo'lga qo'shiladi. Ipak yo'lining asosiy karvon yo'llaridan tashqari ichki savdo yo'llari ham mavjud edi.

Qadimki Marv shahri o'zing qadimiy an'analari va turli geografik qulayliklariga ko'ra Ipak yo'lidagi eng yirik shahar edi. Shuning uchun ham Marvda mahalliy din zardushtiylik ibodatxonlaridan tashqari Hindistonning budda, Vizantiya xiristian olamining tayanchlari bor edi

Ipak yo'li va uning jahon madaniy taraqqiyotidagi ahamiyatini o'rganishda "Tungshi"(Umumiy tarix),"Ziji tunjyan"(hukmdorlar faoliyatiga yordam beruvchi muhim tarixiy voqealar davomi),"Sing Tangshu"(Tang sulolasining yangi tarixi),"Musulmon tabobati","Sinchau chjilu maoyi shi"(Ipak yo'li savdo aloqalari tarixi),"Yuan shi "(Yuan sulolsi tarixi), "Sayyid Ajjol shjarasi", "Syanyang sulolasi","Jeng sulolasi shjarasi","Ma sulolasi shjarasi",Jeng Xe sulolasi tarixi", shuningdek Suyuan Szyanning "G'arbiy hududlar bo'lab sayohat haqida qaydlar" kabi xitoy manbalari muhim o'rin tutadi.

Buyuk Ipak yo'lining IV-XIII sarlar davrini o'rganishda Plono Karpini, Rubruk, Marka Polo (XII), Ibn Faldan (X) kundaliklari, Abu Rayhon Beruniyning "Qadimgi xalqlarda qolgan yodgorliklar", "Hudud ul-olam" (X), Nosir Xusravning "Safarnoma"(XI), Al Hakim at-Termiziyning "Novro'znoma", "Salnoma" (IX), Sadiy SHeroziyning "Sayihatnoma" (XIII), arsab tarixchilari Istaxriy, Yoqut, Al-Maqsiydlarning Markaziy Osiyo to'risidagi qimmatli ma'lumotlar berilgan asarlarida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Xulosa qilib shuni aytilishimiz mumkinki qadimgi karvon yo'llarining yo'nalishi faqatgina geografik shart-sharoitlar bilan bog'liq bo'lmagan, ba'zi vodiylar orqali o'tadigan karvon yo'llari vaqt o'tishi bilan o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotib ketar edi. Ammo Buyuk Ipak yo'li ko'p asrlar davomida sharq va g'arb mamlakatlar hayotida juda katta ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan. Bu yo'l orqali olib borilgan ko'plab savdo va diplomatik munosabatlar orqali mamlakatlarning bir-biriga madaniy va ma'rifiy ta'siri kuchayadi.

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